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The transcriptional landscape of HER2+ subtype breast cancer in humans: CENPU.

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Breast cancer in humans is a solid tumor type with distinct subtypes historically defined by the PAM50 molecular subtype classification scheme (1-3). We utilize, in this study, whole transcriptome technologies to define the transcriptional landscape of HER2+ subtype human breast cancer (4, 5). We describe here differential expression of CENPU in HER2+ breast cancer.

1 We harnessed the power of whole transcriptome technology, using only primary tumor tissues from
2 patients with breast cancer of defined molecular subtype (4, 5) to perform differential gene expression
3 analyses, for characterization, in molecular detail, of the tumor transcriptome of HER2+ subtype breast
4 cancer.

5 **Methods**

6 We utilized microarray datasets GSE45827 (4) and GSE87049 (5) for this global differential gene
7 expression analysis of HER2+ subtype human breast cancer in conjunction with the R-based
8 computational differential gene expression software GEO2R. GSE45827 was generated using
9 [HG-U133_Plus_2] Affymetrix Human Genome U133 Plus 2.0 Array technology with $n=11$ normal breast
10 tissues (control) and $n=30$ HER2+ subtype primary tumors from humans with breast cancer; analysis was
11 performed using GPL570. GSE87049 was generated using Affymetrix Human Gene 1.0 ST Array
12 [transcript (gene) version] technology with $n=35$ normal breast tissues (control) $n=18$ primary breast
13 tumors of HER2+ subtype from humans with breast cancer; analysis was performed using platform
14 GPL6244. We utilized a computational tool to measure the influence of tumor gene expression on overall
15 survival in humans with breast cancer, in $n=1879$ patients (total), in $n=431$ basal subtype patients, in
16 $n=596$ luminal A subtype patients, in $n=439$ luminal B subtype patients, in $n=362$ HER2+ patients, and
17 $n=51$ normal-like subtype patients (6).

18 **Rationale**

19 Breast cancer in humans is a complex molecular entity that remains to be completely defined.

20 **Results**

21 We performed whole transcriptome profiling - subtraction analysis, also known as differential gene
22 expression profiling - to identify and describe at the systems level the complete set of genes whose
23 expression was most specifically activated or repressed in humans with the HER2+ subtype of human
24 breast cancer.

25 1. Primary tumors of the breast from humans with breast cancer: HER2+ subtype

26 $n=11$ normal breast tissues (human)

27 $n=30$ primary tumors (breast; human; HER2+)

ID	<i>p</i> -value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
218883_s_at	3.87E-18	-14.692626	31.188151	-5.035968	CENPU	237/29873	99.2

28 Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in normal breast tissues and HER2+ breast
tumors, we discovered differential expression of centromere protein U, encoded by CENPU (located at
4q35.1) in HER2+ breast cancer in humans (Chart 1). The expression of CENPU changed more than
99% of the human breast and breast tumor transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose
expression was measured - in this case, 29,873 transcripts ("Rank"). Note the negative fold-change
indicating increased quantity of CENPU messenger RNA in HER2+ subtype tumors, demonstrating
up-regulation of CENPU during transformation of the breast from normal breast tissue to HER2+ breast
cancer.

2. Primary tumors of the breast from humans with breast cancer: HER2+ subtype

$n=35$ normal breast tissues (human)

$n=18$ primary tumors (breast; human; HER2+)

ID	<i>p</i> -value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
8103932	5.31E-10	-7.5431973	12.6380564	-1.46576147	CENPU	713/33297	97.9

Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in normal breast tissues and HER2+ breast tumors in a second microarray dataset from independent investigators and a separate patient cohort, we validated differential expression of CENPU in HER2+ breast cancer in humans (Chart 2). The expression of CENPU here changed more than 97% of the human breast and breast tumor transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 33,297 transcripts (“Rank”). Note the negative fold-change indicating increased quantity of CENPU messenger RNA in HER2+ subtype tumors, demonstrating up-regulation of CENPU during transformation of the breast from normal breast tissue to HER2+ breast cancer.

Thus, CENPU is a gene whose differential expression defines the transcriptional landscape of the HER2+ breast cancer subtype in humans.

Finally, we measured the influence of CENPU tumor gene expression on overall survival in humans with breast cancer using a computational tool (Figure 1) (6).

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Fig. 1: Relationship between CENPU tumor expression and overall survival in humans with breast cancer.
Caption: Overall survival in all patients (above; left), in patients with basal subtype (above; center), in patients with luminal A subtype (above; right), in patients with luminal B subtype (below; left), in patients with HER2+ subtype (below; center), and patients with normal-like subtype breast cancer (below; right) is depicted in these Kaplan-Meier plots.

Discussion

We describe here CENPU as a component gene product of the HER2+ subtype in human breast cancer, suggesting its importance in the development or maintenance of the subtype, a product of tumor evolution in transformation of solid tissues in humans.

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